

Synthesis, spectral, gamma ray irradiation, surface morphology and thermal studies of some Ru^{III} complexes of an azo dye derived from 4-aminoantipyrene

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Abstract : Synthesis of some novel Ru^{III} complexes with an azo dye methoxyphenolazoantipyrene (HL) derived from 4-aminoantipyrene and 2-methoxyphenol are reported. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data, IR, UV-Vis, EPR and FAB mass spectral studies. The physico-chemical studies and spectral data indicate that HL acts as a bidentate chelating ligand. The effect of gamma ray irradiation on the thermal behaviour and the surface morphology of a selected complex [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] (I) was studied. The electrochemical behaviour of the complex (I) was investigated by cyclic voltammetry. All the complexes are found to be neutral and an octahedral geometry has been tentatively proposed. The ligand HL and complexes were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity. The 3D molecular modeling and analysis of bond lengths and bond angles have been carried out for the complex (I).

Keywords : Azo dye, Ru^{III} complexes, γ -ray irradiation, surface morphology.

Introduction

The growing interest of chemists in the study of Ru^{III} complexes is due to their fascinating electron transfer and energy transfer properties¹⁻⁴. There has been considerable interest in ruthenium complexes now-a-days because of their redox stability, excited state life time and excited state reactivities⁵. Ruthenium offers a wide range of oxidation states and the reactivities of the ruthenium complexes depend on the stability and interconvertibility of these oxidation states, which, in turn, depends on the nature of the ligands bound to the metal. Complexation of ruthenium by ligands of different types has, thus been of particular interest⁶. Change in coordination environment around ruthenium plays an important role in modulating the properties of the complexes. The presence of nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms turns the properties of the complexes to a great extent as effective and stereospecific catalysts for oxidation, reduction and hydrolysis⁷⁻⁹. These types of complexes are also reported to have carcinostatic, antitumour, antiviral and antibacterial activity¹⁰. A survey of literature shows that very few Ru^{III} complexes of azo dyes derived from biologically active molecule 4-aminoantipyrene have been reported¹¹.

In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of some new complexes of Ru^{III} with a potentially bidentate ligand, methoxyphenolazoantipyrene (HL) (Fig. 1). As irradiation may induce changes in textural, structural, electric, thermal and magnetic properties of a large variety of solids¹². An abundant literature is available on thermal studies of irradiated salts¹³ while the same in metal complexes is still rare¹⁴. The effect of gamma ray irradiation on the thermal behaviour and the surface morphology of one of the complex was studied in detail in the present investigation.

Fig. 1. Structure of methoxyphenolazoantipyrene, HL.

Results and discussion

All the chelates are deeply coloured, fairly stable at room temperature and possess good keeping qualities.

They are non-hygroscopic solids and soluble in common organic solvents, like acetone, chloroform, methanol, acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO. The molar conductances of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes exhibited a value less than $20 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in dry methanol and indicate their non-electrolyte behaviour. The analytical data are listed in Table 1.

Table 2 lists the tentative assignments of main IR bands of metal complexes for the ligand HL in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region. The spectrum of the ligand HL (Fig. 7) exhibits a broad medium band at 2925 cm^{-1} is assigned to hydrogen bonded -OH group^{15,16}. In the spectra of the complexes, a new broad band appears $\sim 3440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of free -OH group and hence its non participation in coordination with the metal ion⁵⁻⁷. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the pyrazolone ring observed at 1634 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the free ligand is shifted to lower frequency of $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes confirming the involvement of the C=O group in complexation^{17,18}. The vibrational band observed at 1465 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ group in the ligand is shifted to $\sim 1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in

the spectra of all the complexes suggesting the participation of the azo group in coordination with the metal ion¹⁹. Thus the ligand exhibit a neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes, coordinating through the C=O and -N=N- groups only. The bands due to coordinated PPh₃ group usually observed in the range $1436\text{--}1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ could not be located in the spectra of all the complexes due to its overlapping with the azo group vibrations¹⁵. The bands ~ 520 , 696 and 749 cm^{-1} are assigned to PPh₃ fragments in the spectra of the complexes^{20,21}.

In the IR spectra of nitrate complex of HL, the three additional bands 1495 , 1385 and 1023 cm^{-1} which are not present in the spectra of the ligands, are attributed to ν_5 , ν_1 and ν_3 modes of the coordinated nitrate ion. Since the difference between ν_5 and ν_1 is 110 cm^{-1} , it is suggested that the nitrate ion is coordinated monodentately to the metal ion. The thiocyanate complexes show very strong band at 2054 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{C-N}}$), medium intensity bands at 744 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$) and 480 cm^{-1} (δ NCS) confirming N-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group¹¹. Two split

Table 1. Analytical data of ligand and complexes

Ligand/Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					μ_{eff}
	C	H	N	Cl	S	
HL	63.1 (63.90)	5.26 (5.32)	16.32 (16.5)	-	-	-
[RuCl ₃ (PPh ₃)(HL)] (I)	53.41 (53.53)	4.39 (4.45)	6.72 (6.93)	12.82 (13.6)	-	1.94
[RuCl ₂ (NCS)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (II)	53.36 (53.47)	4.4 (4.33)	8.34 (8.43)	7.92 (8.53)	3.66 (3.8)	1.96
[RuCl ₂ (NO ₃)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (III)	51.46 (51.78)	4.18 (4.31)	8.26 (8.39)	7.98 (8.49)	-	1.98
[RuCl ₂ (ClO ₄)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (IV)	52.44 (52.87)	3.52 (3.78)	6.2 (6.42)	11.82 (12.9)	-	1.95

Table 2. Important IR spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of ligand and complexes

Ligand/Complex	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{O-H})$	$\nu(\text{C=O})$	$\nu(\text{N=N})$
	free	hydrogen bonded	pyra-zolone	
HL	-	2925	1634	1465
[RuCl ₃ (PPh ₃)(HL)] (I)	3435	-	1585	1434
[RuCl ₂ (NCS)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (II)	3440	-	1591	1433
[RuCl ₂ (NO ₃)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (III)	3433	-	1603	1436
[RuCl ₂ (ClO ₄)(PPh ₃)(HL)] (IV)	3432	-	1583	1435

bands observed ~ 1120 and $\sim 1091 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to ν_4 and ν_1 and another set of split bands, ~ 640 and $\sim 610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, assigned to ν_3 and ν_5 vibrations are characteristic of monodentately coordinated perchlorate group²². This is supported by the molar conductance data.

The ¹H NMR spectrum²³ of the free ligand HL (Fig. 7) showed a sharp signal at δ 12.505 (phenolic OH). The spectrum displays three singlets, which correspond to methyl protons. The $>\text{C-CH}_3$ group of pyrazolone ring appears as a sharp singlet in the region δ 2.62 while the

$>N-CH_3$ signal is observed as another singlet in the region δ 3.30 and $-OCH_3$ signal is observed at δ 3.819. The signal due to five aromatic protons of the antipyrine phenyl ring appear as multiplet between δ 7.29–7.44 and these due to the protons of phenyl rings are observed as multiplet between δ 6.67–6.78.

All the ruthenium complexes show magnetic moment values in the range 1.92–2.00 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron, suggesting a low spin t_{2g}^5 configuration for the Ru^{III} ion in an octahedral environment in all of these complexes⁶.

The electronic spectral bands of the complexes in methanol with tentative assignments are discussed. All the Ru^{III} complexes are paramagnetic, indicating the presence of ruthenium in the +3 oxidation state. The ground state of Ru^{III} (t_{2g}^5 configuration) is ${}^2T_{2g}$ and the first excited doublet levels in the order of increasing energy are ${}^2A_{2g}$ and ${}^2T_{1g}$ which arise from the $t_{2g}^4 e_g^1$ configuration. The electronic spectra of Ru^{III} complexes in methanol show two to three bands in the region 510–345 nm. But in most of the Ru^{III} complexes, the spectra show only charge transfer bands²⁵. In the electronic spectra of the complexes, the bands appearing in the region 570–480 nm are assigned to ${}^2T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ transition. Thus the nature of the electronic spectra of all the complexes indicates an octahedral geometry around ruthenium ion in the complexes and the spectra are very similar to the ones observed for other Ru^{III} complexes²⁶.

Mass spectroscopy, which is mainly applied in the analysis of biomolecules, has been increasingly used as a powerful structural characterization technique in coordination chemistry. The FAB mass spectra of HL (Fig. 7) and one of its complexes (I) were recorded and their stoichiometric compositions were compared. The molecular ion peak for the HL shows peak at 339.77 m/z ($C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_3$), corresponding to 338.36, where as its

complex shows the molecular ion peak at 808.08 [$RuCl_3(PPh_3)(C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_3)$], which shows the stoichiometry of the complex as [$RuCl_3(PPh_3)(HL)$]. The peaks at m/z 772.63 $[M-Cl]^+$ and 701.73 $[M-Cl-Cl-Cl]^+$ and 439.43 $[M-Cl-Cl-Cl-PPh_3]^+$ in the complex suggests the presence of three chloride ions and one PPh_3 in the complex^{27,28}.

The electrochemical behavior (Fig. 2) of complex (I) was examined by cyclic voltammetry in the potential range from -2000 mV to $+2000$ mV at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} after deaerating 10^{-3} M solution of the complex in acetonitrile with tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate as the supporting electrolyte. The cyclic voltammogram of the complex showed only oxidation potential (Ru^{IV}/Ru^{III}). The reason for irreversibility for these complexes may be due to short lived oxidation state of the metal ion or due to the oxidative degradation of the ligands²⁹.

The nature and extend of the subtle distortions of grossly octahedral environment of low spin d^5 ions can be studied by EPR spectra. X-band EPR spectrum (Fig. 3) of complex (I) was recorded in the polycrystal-

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of [$RuCl_3(PPh_3)(HL)$] (I).

Fig. 3. EPR spectrum of [$RuCl_3(PPh_3)(HL)$].

line form at liquid nitrogen temperature. The complex exhibits three lines with different 'g' values ($g_x = 2.28$, $g_y = 2.0027$, $g_z = 1.96$) ($g_x \neq g_y \neq g_z$) indicating the presence of magnetic anisotropy. The average g value was found to be ~ 2.09 . These values are in the range that are obtained for similar other Ru^{III} complexes²⁶. Three g values observed for the complex indicates rhombohedral distortion of octahedral geometry³⁰.

Irradiation studies :

Thermal behavior and surface morphology of the complex (I) were studied before and after gamma irradiation.

No colour change occurred upon irradiation, indicating the absence of colour centers in the sample.

The SEM micrographs of the ligand and complex are shown in Fig. 4. The SEM image of the ligand is shown in Fig. 4a. The SEM images reveal an amorphous nature for the ligand. However, after complex formation, a drastic change in morphology can be observed. The SEM images of the Ru^{III} complex before irradiation (Figs. 4b and 4c) distinctly reveal the presence of porous structure for the complex, the pore size being in the nano-meter range. The formation of inter-aggregated voids is closely related to the solution conditions, which may have significant effects on the surface physical chemistry of the synthesised complex. The Ru^{III} complex was γ irradiated and the SEM micrographs of the irradiated samples are shown in Figs. 4d and 4e. As evident from the SEM images, the porous nature of the complex has been lost on irradiation. The induced changes in the surface characteristics of solids due to γ -irradiation could be attributed to splitting of their crystallites³¹, desorption of chemisorbed oxygen³², removal of surface hydroxyl groups³³, pore wall erosion and progressive blocking of pores as bulk expansion took place³¹⁻³⁴.

Thermal behavior of the complex [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] before and after gamma irradiation were studied by TGA and DTG techniques by heating in air at a rate of 10 °C per min. Thermal curves were redrawn as percentage mass vs temperature curves and presented in Fig. 5. The thermal decomposition results are given in Table 3.

Thermograms of unirradiated and irradiated samples are essentially similar in each case. Thermal decomposition of unirradiated and irradiated samples of [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] proceeds in two stages. Percentage

mass loss during the first stage in each case suggests the departure of the ligand part of the complex and the second stage accounts for the oxidative decomposition of the remaining part of the complex to give Ru₂O₃ as the ultimate residue. Thermograms of unirradiated and irradiated samples are essentially of the same pattern. It is evident that decomposition is relatively faster in the irradiated sample but does not alter the reaction interval significantly. It can be noted that irradiation results in lowering of reactivity parameters. The enhanced reactivity of irradiated sample has been ascribed to lattice defects as well as products of chemical damage. Systems in which thermal decomposition are accompanied by melting, the lattice defects introduced by irradiation do not have any significant role. Thus the enhancement is due to damage fragments only³⁵.

Kinetic parameters viz. activation energy (E), frequency factor (Z) and entropy of activation (ΔS) were evaluated by the integral method following Coats-Redfern equation. The results along with correlation coefficient (r) are presented in Table 4. The values of $\log g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T \times 10^3$ plots were linear (Figs. 6a, 6b, 6c and 6d). The fitness was tested by evaluating the correlation coefficient (Tables 5a, 5b, 5c and 5d). The values of activation energy (E_{act}) were obtained from the slope of pre-exponential factor (A) from the intercept of the straight line. The entropy of activation (ΔS) was also estimated.

Thermal studies reveal that irradiation enhances thermal decomposition leading to a decrease in thermal and kinetic parameters.

Irradiation changed the surface morphology as is evident from SEM images. Changes in the scanning electron micrographs indicate that the applied dose can cause changes in the surface morphology of crystals.

The *in vitro* biological screening effects of the investigated ligand and compounds were tested against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv, *E. coli* and *Lactobacillus leichmannii* by the Resazurin assay method. All the synthesized complexes exhibited activity at 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv and active against *E. coli* at 100, 10 and 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The complexes were not active against *Lactobacillus leichmannii*.

The toxicity of the complexes can be related to the strength of the metal ligand bond, along with other fac-

Fig. 4a. Ligand (HL).

Fig. 4b, 4c. Complex (I) unirradiated.

Fig. 4d, 4e. Complex (I) irradiated to 800 kGy.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of ligand and complex.

tors, such as the size of the cation receptor sites, chelation effect of metal ions on the normal cell membrane, and a combined effect of the metal and ligand for inactivation of the biomolecules³⁶. Chelation may enhance or suppress the biochemical potential of bioactive organic species. Some important factors which determine the acti-

vity are the following : the nature of the metal ion, nature of the ligand, geometry of the complex, concentration, hydrophilicity, lipophilicity and presence of co-ligand^{37,38}. Steric and pharmacokinetic factors also play vital roles in deciding the potency of an antimicrobial agent. Metal chelates bear polar and nonpolar properties together. This

Fig. 5. TG and DTG curves of unirradiated and irradiated $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$.

Table 3. Thermal decomposition data of $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$

Complexes	Stages of decomposition	Decomposition temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)			Weight loss (%)
		T_i	T_f	T_s	
$[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ Unirradiated	I	193	312	233	41.63
$[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ Irradiated to 800 kGy	I	174	271	213	38.61
$[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ Unirradiated	II	431	519	475	27.09
$[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ Irradiated to 800 kGy	II	419	490	456	29.78

Fig. 6a. Coats-Redfern plot for stage I decomposition of unirradiated $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$.

Fig. 6b. Coats-Redfern plot for stage II decomposition of unirradiated $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$.

Fig. 6c. Coats-Redfern plot for stage I decomposition $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ irradiated to 800 kGy.

Fig. 6d. Coats-Redfern plot for stage II decomposition $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$ irradiated to 800 kGy.

Table 4. Kinetic parameters evaluated by Coats-Redfern method

Complex	Stage	E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	A (s ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Correlation coefficient (r)
[RuCl ₃ (PPh ₃)(HL)]	I	160.41	2.21×10^{14}	31.74	0.9940
Unirradiated	II	401.81	1.13×10^{22}	249.95	0.9963
[RuCl ₃ (PPh ₃)(HL)]	I	138.97	6.25×10^{12}	2.85	0.9917
Irradiated to 800 kGy	II	285.50	2.59×10^{18}	104.05	0.9998

Table 5a. Computational details for the stage I decomposition of unirradiated [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)]

T (°C)	Mass (%)	$n = 2$			$r = 0.9940$		
		TK	RT	W	A	$g\alpha$	CR
190	96.92737	463	2.15983	0	0	0	-
200	96.08939	473	2.11416	0.83798	0.02174	0.0222	-16.12597
210	94.69274	483	2.07039	2.23463	0.05797	0.06135	-15.15114
220	91.06145	493	2.0284	5.86592	0.15217	0.17797	-14.12714
230	84.07821	503	1.98807	12.84916	0.33333	0.48933	-13.1559
240	77.09497	513	1.94932	19.8324	0.51449	1.01792	-12.46279
250	70.94972	523	1.91205	25.97765	0.67391	1.93508	-11.85901
260	66.48045	533	1.87617	30.44692	0.78986	3.41255	-11.32958
270	63.12849	543	1.84162	33.79888	0.87681	6.2044	-10.76896
280	60.89385	553	1.80832	36.03352	0.93478	11.85565	-10.15791
290	59.77654	563	1.7762	37.15083	0.96377	20.89661	-9.62697
300	59.21788	573	1.7452	37.70949	0.97826	33.74179	-9.18303
310	58.37989	583	1.71527	38.54748	1	-	-

Table 5b. Computational details for the stage II decomposition of unirradiated [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)]

T (°C)	Mass (%)	$n = 1.9$			$r = 0.9963$		
		TK	RT	W	α	$g\alpha$	CR
440	55.02793	713	1.40252	0	0	0	-
450	53.35196	723	1.38313	1.67597	0.07059	0.07483	-15.75929
460	51.67598	733	1.36426	3.35195	0.14118	0.15936	-15.0309
470	48.04469	743	1.3459	6.98324	0.29412	0.38738	-14.16975
480	41.06145	753	1.32802	13.96648	0.58824	1.17164	-13.08973
490	36.03352	763	1.31062	18.99441	0.8	2.71088	-12.27724
500	33.51955	773	1.29366	21.50838	0.90588	5.21426	-11.64916
510	31.84358	783	1.27714	23.18435	0.97647	14.14151	-10.67715
520	31.28492	793	1.26103	23.74301	1	-	-

Table 5c. Computational details for the stage I decomposition of [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] irradiated to 800 kGy

T (°C)	Mass (%)	$n = 2$			$r = 0.9917$		
		TK	RT	W	α	$g\alpha$	CR
170	98.78419	443	2.25734	0	0	0	-
180	97.56839	453	2.20751	1.2158	0.03252	0.03361	-15.62462
190	95.13678	463	2.15983	3.64741	0.09756	0.10811	-14.50008
200	91.48936	473	2.11416	7.29483	0.19512	0.24242	-13.73526
210	84.80243	483	2.07039	13.98176	0.37398	0.5974	-12.8752

220	78.7234	493	2.0284	20.06079	0.53659	1.1579	-12.25441
230	73.25228	503	1.98807	25.53191	0.68293	2.15385	-11.67393
240	68.99696	513	1.94932	29.78723	0.79675	3.92	-11.11446
250	66.56535	523	1.91205	32.21884	0.86179	6.2353	-10.68894
260	63.52584	533	1.87617	35.25835	0.94309	16.57142	-9.74936
270	61.39818	543	1.84162	37.38601	1	0	-

Table 5d. Computational details for the stage II decomposition of [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] irradiated to 800 kGy

<i>T</i> (°C)	<i>n</i> = 1.2			<i>r</i> = 0.9998			CR
	Mass (%)	TK	RT	W	α	<i>g</i> α	
420	60.79027	693	1.443	0	0	0	-
430	57.14286	703	1.42248	3.64741	0.125	0.13533	-15.11075
440	53.79939	713	1.40252	6.99088	0.23958	0.28153	-14.40648
450	48.93617	723	1.38313	11.8541	0.40625	0.54944	-13.76567
460	42.24924	733	1.36426	18.54103	0.63542	1.11802	-13.08274
470	36.77812	743	1.3459	24.01215	0.82292	2.06862	-12.49451
480	33.1307	753	1.32802	27.65957	0.94792	4.0288	-11.85466
490	31.61094	763	1.31062	29.17933	1	-	-

makes them suitable for permeation from the cells and tissues. Changing hydrophilicity and lipophilicity probably leads to bringing down the solubility and permeability barriers of cell, which in turn enhances the bioavailability of chemotherapeutics, on the one hand, and potentiality on the other hand. It can be considered that these compounds deactivate various cellular enzymes, which play a vital role in various metabolic pathways of these microorganisms³⁹.

It can also be inferred that the ultimate action of the complex is the denaturation of one or more proteins of the cell, which, as a result, impairs the normal cellular processes²⁸.

The molecular modeling of the proposed configuration of (Fig. 8.) complex (I), as a representative, were constructed using the Ultra molecular modeling and analysis⁴⁰ Software CHEM Bio Office 2008. The actual bond length and bond angles are given in Table 6. They were calculated as a result of energy minimization in CHEM 3D, while the optimal bond length and optimal bond angle values are the most desirable/favorable (standard) bond lengths and bond angles established by the builder unit of the CHEM 3D. In most cases, the actual bond length and bond angles are close to the optimal values, and thus the proposed structure of the compound as well as the others are acceptable⁴¹.

X-Ray powder photograph obtained for the complex (I) recorded only very few reflections and hence could not be indexed. This may be an indication of the amorphous nature of the complexes.

On the basis of all the above spectral data and physico-chemical studies, a distorted octahedral geometry (Fig. 9) has been tentatively proposed for the complexes.

Experimental

Materials :

RuCl₃·3H₂O (Loba Chemie, Mumbai, India) was used. All other chemicals were of AR grade.

Physical measurements :

Chloride was estimated by standard method⁴². Analysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content of the ligand and its complexes were carried out on a Vario EL-III CHN Elemental analyzer at the SAIF, Cochin University of Science and Technology, India. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrometer using KBr pellets in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Electronic spectra were recorded in methanol on a Shimadzu UV-2450 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR spectra of ligand, HL was recorded using Bruker DRX-500 NMR spectrometer with TMS as the standard at NIIST, Thiruvananthapuram, India. EPR spectra of complex (I) in polycrystalline state at liquid nitrogen temperature re-

Fig. 8. Energy optimized configuration of $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$.

Fig. 9. Proposed 2D structure of $[\text{RuCl}_2\text{X}(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$.

recorded on a Varian E-112 spectrometer at X-band, using TCNE as marker with 100 kHz modulation frequency and 9.1 GHz microwave frequency at the SAIF, IIT, Mumbai, India. The molar conductances of the complexes in methanol solutions (10^{-3} M) at room temperature were measured using a Systronics direct reading conductivity

Table 6. Selected bond lengths and bond angles of $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{HL})]$

Atoms	Bond length (Å)	Atoms	Bond angle (deg.)
Ru(13)-Cl(17)	2.2494	Cl(17)-Ru(13)-P(16)	93.7078
Ru(13)-P(16)	2.3558	Cl(17)-Ru(13)-Cl(15)	86.0651
Ru(13)-Cl(15)	2.2497	Cl(17)-Ru(13)-Cl(14)	94.4813
Ru(13)-Cl(14)	2.2500	Cl(17)-Ru(13)-O(9)	85.9067
O(9)-Ru(13)	1.8826	Cl(17)-Ru(13)-N(6)	147.1799
N(6)-Ru(13)	1.9632	P(16)-Ru(13)-Cl(15)	97.0134
		P(16)-Ru(13)-Cl(14)	90.7873
		P(16)-Ru(13)-O(9)	170.4607
		P(16)-Ru(13)-N(6)	119.0811
		Cl(15)-Ru(13)-Cl(14)	172.1323
		Cl(15)-Ru(13)-O(9)	92.4716
		Cl(15)-Ru(13)-N(6)	88.3561
		Cl(14)-Ru(13)-O(9)	79.7490
		Cl(14)-Ru(13)-N(6)	86.9495
		O(9)-Ru(13)-N(6)	62.0367

meter. The magnetic susceptibilities were recorded at room temperature by the Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants⁴³. Thermal analyses of the complexes were carried out by heating in air at a rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ on a Perkin-Elmer, Diamond TG/DTA Analyser. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were recorded using a Philips X-ray PW1710 diffractometer. The FAB mass spectrum of HL and complex (I) were recorded on a Jeol JMS600H mass spectrometer. The samples were subjected to gamma irradiation to a dose of 800 kGy using ^{60}Co γ -ray in gamma chamber 5000 cc self shielded at constant intensity under room temperature at a dose rate of 1.85 kGy h^{-1} at Rubber Research Institute of India (RRII), Kottayam.

Irradiation :

The dried samples sealed in pyrex ampoules were subjected to gamma irradiation to a dose of 800 kGy using ^{60}Co γ -ray in Gamma chamber 5000 cc self shielded at constant intensity under room temperature at a dose rate of 1.85 kGy h^{-1} . Irradiated samples were taken out, mixed uniformly and kept in desiccator over P_2O_5 .

Antimicrobial experiments :

Antitubercular activity of HL and complexes against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv and antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Lactobacillus leichmannii* were done

by the Resazurin assay method at the Rajeev Gandhi Centre for Biotechnology (Thiruvananthapuram).

The effects of the extracts were checked for their activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv in 96 well microtitre plates. The medium used was Middlebrook 7H9 broth (Difco BBL) (containing OADC supplement and 0.5% glycerol). The compounds were added to 180 μ L of the medium taken in microtitre well plates to make final concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 μ g/ml. To these tubes, 20 μ L of the *M. tuberculosis* culture diluted to McFarland standard 1.0 was added. Control tubes consisted of the medium with the bacterial culture to which the same volume of DMF was added. Negative control consisted of medium and dyes alone without any culture. Rifampicin, a standard antituberculosis drug at 0.5 μ g/ml acted as a positive control. The tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 7 days. At the end of incubation 20 μ L of 0.01% of Resazurin (Sigma) dye was added to the tubes and kept for incubation until the dye turned pink in the control tubes. After incubation the tubes were checked for colour change. Change of colour from blue to pink would indicate growth while lack of colour change would suggest inhibition of growth (Blue colour = inhibition. Pink = no inhibition).

Synthesis of ligand : HL :

Synthesis of ligand was carried out by 4-aminoantipyrine and 2-methoxyphenol as the case may be by diazotization and coupling as reported earlier¹⁵. 4-aminoantipyrine (10 g, 50 mmol) was converted to the hydrochloride using 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (28 ml) and the solution was cooled below 0 °C in an ice-salt bath. A solution of sodium nitrite (3.8 g, 55 mmol) in water (20 ml) was chilled using the ice-salt bath.

The pre-cooled nitrite solution was then added in small volumes to the cold amine hydrochloride solution with good stirring. The temperature was always kept below 10 °C and small amounts of crushed ice were used when required. The last part of the nitrite solution was added slowly and dropwise till a slight excess of nitrous acid was present which was indicated by an immediate blue colour, imparted to a starch potassium iodide paper. After keeping the diazonium chloride solution in ice bath for a few min, the temperature was allowed to rise to about 5 °C.

2-Methoxyphenol (7 ml, 50 mmol) was dissolved in 45 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was then cooled below 5 °C in an ice bath followed by the direct addition of ~25 g of crushed ice. The cold diazonium chloride solution was added very slowly to the solution of 2-methoxyphenol with vigorous stirring. The colour of the solution became reddish yellow and a solid product separated slowly. After the addition of the entire amount of diazo compound, the mixture was allowed to stand in the bath for about 30 min with occasional stirring. The solid product obtained was then filtered under gentle suction, washed well with cold water and recrystallized from alcohol. The purity was tested by TLC. The ligand was characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV, FAB mass and NMR spectra.

Synthesis of Ru^{III} complexes :

The starting complex [RuCl₃(PPh₃)₃] was prepared by the reported procedure¹⁶.

The following method was adopted for the preparation of [RuCl₃(PPh₃)(HL)] (I). To a solution of [RuCl₃(PPh₃)₃] (2 mmol) in 20 ml benzene, a methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol, 20 ml) was added. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for 5–6 h. The resulting solution was concentrated. On adding a small amount of petroleum ether, the solid separated was suction filtered washed with benzene and dried *in vacuo* over P₄O₁₀.

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of thiocyanate, nitrate, and perchlorate complexes. [RuCl₃(PPh₃)₃] (2 mmol) in 20 ml benzene, containing 2 mmol of NH₄NCS/2 mmol of LiNO₃/1–2 drops of perchloric acid as the case may be, was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol, 20 ml). All complexes, except the thiocyanate complex, were precipitated on refluxing the solution for ~5–6 h. The thiocyanate complex was precipitated on stirring the solution at 40 °C for 20–25 min. The resulting solution was concentrated. On adding a small amount of petroleum ether, the solid separated was suction filtered washed with benzene and dried *in vacuo* over P₄O₁₀.

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